

CONTRIBUTION OF THE COMMUNICATION SYSTEM TO THE USE OF MEDIA IN DISASTER MANAGEMENT IN SOUTHEAST SULAWESI

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to analyze the significant contribution of the communication system in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), and coordination (X3) to the use of media (Y1) in disaster management in Kendari City and North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This research method uses a survey method with a quantitative research approach. In this study, the variables in question are information sharing (X1), cooperation (X2), coordination (X3) to the media (Y1). Sampling using proportional sampling technique as many as 60 samples. Data collection techniques through questionnaires to respondents for primary data, while observation and interviews as complementary methods of data collection. Calculations for reliability testing are carried out through the SPSS 25 computer program. The results of the study showed that the communication system for natural disaster emergency response in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) had a strong and significant effect simultaneously on the use of media (Y1) in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency. However, the communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) has a simultaneous but not significant effect on the use of media in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

Keywords: Communication System, Media, Disaster Management, Southeast Sulawesi

INTRODUCTION

Communication as a science and a practical activity in everyday life is increasingly considered important, where communication is something that is needed every day as a form of exchanging information between human beings. Disaster communication has recently become a popular concept in the communication and disaster fields, although research on disaster communication has begun to be widely carried out. However, in Indonesia itself, research related to disaster communication only began to be carried out after the earthquake and tsunami in Aceh in 2004. However, awareness about the importance of communication in disaster management is increasing. One of the important points of concern regarding communication in disasters is the issue of uncertainty (Haddow & Haddow, 2013).

No activity is fundamental to our social, personal, or professional lives except through communication (Rubben & Steward 2013). Communication is an important thing in human

life. Furthermore, awareness of communication activities is one of the fundamental processes, at the same time implying that it is easy to understand and control. On the other hand, communication activities are very complex. There are many examples in personal, community, and professional life.

The fundamental purpose of communication is to control our physical and psychological environment. Humans have no choice but to establish social contact with other people and their environment. Of course, this happens through communication. Communication is not only a fundamental activity of human life but also has an important purpose to perform tasks that are essential to human needs and to build and cultivate relationships with other people. With this reality, communication science is increasingly recognized as no longer as a monodisciplinary science based on political science but tends to be increasingly recognized as a multidisciplinary science that is open and fostered by many disciplines.

Southeast Sulawesi Province is one of the areas in Indonesia that is at high risk of being affected by disasters, especially disasters related to weather and climate or known as hydrometeorological disasters. Many disasters occurred in the period 2013-2019 causing a lot of damage to vital infrastructure in this region, and not a few materials and non-material losses that became a burden on both the government and the community. Communication arises from the need to reduce uncertainty to act effectively to protect or strengthen the total interest in individual or group interactions (Little John & Foss, 2010).

Disaster communication is important not only during an emergency during disaster but also before a disaster. Communication is the best way to mitigate, prepare for, respond to and recover from a disaster situation. The ability to convey disaster messages to the public, governments, media, and community leaders can reduce disaster risk, save lives, and reduce the impact of disasters (Hadow & Hadow, 2013).

Disaster management must be supported by various approaches, the first with soft power, namely by preparing community preparedness through socialization and providing information about disasters. And the second with hard power, namely efforts to deal with disasters with physical development. On the other hand, the development of the Internet of Things (IoT) and big data technology greatly help mitigation to be more effective and more accurate. The use of this technology can realize 4.0 mitigation which is very important in reducing the risk of natural disasters. By using big data and IoT, the flood early warning system can be better. Water flow control for flood prevention can be carried out more quickly by the measurable capacity of the disaster. Global awareness of disasters has increased since climate change emerged.

A series of disasters must realize the importance of realizing a strong mitigation system. Poor mitigation so far has been exacerbated by the absence of local government crisis management. The weakness of the local government's mitigation system has the effect of losing control after the disaster.

The implementer of disaster management according to the law is the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB). This agency requires accurate data during a disaster so that it

can respond quickly, precisely, coordinated, and comprehensively with relevant government agencies. It is always important to improve the mitigation system and emergency response mechanism quickly and precisely with the help of the latest technology.

By providing up-to-date accurate geospatial information, emergency response and reconstruction programs can be better. Geospatial data platforms such as open street maps, mapping projects that are open source allow to estimate the extent of damage quickly and monitor the implementation of disaster management.

Southeast Sulawesi Province is an area that is very prone to disasters. In addition to being an area located in a subduction zone which causes a very potential for earthquakes due to the activity of tectonic plates, these plates move relative to one another, resulting in shifts and collisions that will cause a buildup of energy that has the potential to cause an earthquake.

In the Kendari City Disaster Management Emergency Plan (RKPB) document (2019) it is explained that the Southeast Sulawesi Province area is quite potential for seismic earthquakes, it appears that the earthquake points (epicenters) are spread throughout the peninsula of Southeast Sulawesi Province.

In addition, Southeast Sulawesi Province is an area that is at high risk of being affected by weather and climate-related disasters or hydrometeorological disasters. The number of disaster events in the 2013–2019 period caused a lot of vital infrastructure in this region to be damaged and not a few materials and non-material losses that became a burden for all parties, both the government and the community. These various disasters are certain to disrupt the process of sustainable development planning, damage sustainable ecosystems, and the environment, and contribute to the increase in poverty and other social problems. For example, by processing data from the Indonesian Disaster Information Data (DIBI) of the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB), the floods that hit Southeast Sulawesi Province in 2009 reached 413 incidents with 118 fatalities and a total of 131,920 residents had to evacuate. For damage, houses were heavily damaged reaching 3,969 units and 15,827 houses were slightly damaged.

According to BNPB, Southeast Sulawesi Province is quite a potential for seismic earthquakes, it appears that the earthquake points (epicenters) are spread along the peninsula of Southeast Sulawesi Province, both in this case Kendari City and North Konawe Regency.

Kendari City is part of the Indonesian archipelago which has a very high potential for disasters and also varies greatly in terms of types of disasters. These natural conditions cause the risk of natural disasters to occur.

From 2017 to 2020 the flood disaster that occurred in Kendari City was almost evenly distributed in all sub-districts, with a total of 44 incidents in 2017 in 10 sub-districts in Kendari City, then in 2018 it decreased to 39 the number of events, in 2019 again decreased to 27 the number of disaster events, and in 2020 it decreased again to 10 the number of disaster events spread over 11 sub-districts in Kendari City. In addition to the flood disaster, Kendari City also experienced earthquakes with a total of 19 incidents in 2017, in 2018 there

were 20 incidents, in 2019 there were 33 incidents, and in 2020 there were 3 events. Another natural disaster that occurred in Kendari City was landslides, with a total of 28 incidents since 2017, 18 in 2018, 20 in 2019, and 7 in 2020.

Apart from Kendari City which is a disaster-prone area, North Konawe Regency which is also located in Southeast Sulawesi Province is also a disaster-prone district. Historically, North Konawe Regency has a moderate to the high level of disaster risk. The high-risk level for earthquakes, landslides, floods, flash floods, droughts, extreme weather, extreme waves, and abrasion, as well as forest and land fires. While the level of risk is low, such as the occurrence of a tsunami. This is an example of how local governments and stakeholders can shape disaster risk mitigation efforts to help implement emergency response plans for disaster management in the North Konawe region.

Based on the Indonesian Disaster Data and Information (DIBI), the recorded period of events in the North Konawe Regency is from 2004-to 2018. In that span of years, North Konawe Regency has experienced 6 (six) types of disasters that have occurred. These disasters include floods, landslides, droughts, earthquakes, cyclones, and fires.

Various regulatory products in dealing with disasters have been made, but in reality, there are still various shortcomings in disaster management practices. One example of the practice of disaster communication management that has not been maximized can be seen in the earthquake disaster.

Factors of cooperation and collaboration are key factors in disaster management. The problem in disaster management lies in coordination (Prizzia 2008). Disaster management requires good coordination. The effectiveness of the response depends on the coordination among the departments that have responsibility for the disaster. If you look at the condition of disaster management in Indonesia, the results of research conducted by Ross can be taken into consideration that disaster management requires effective coordination.

On the other hand, the media aspect also plays an important role in disaster management. Especially the role of television media in showing the (same) picture repeatedly for days without drawing a line of relevance to the actuality of events. Media becomes redundant and loses its essence and context.

As an information provider institution, the media has become the center of public attention, in particular the various disaster events that occurred in Indonesia. Positively the media can be the first source to inform events, show developments and psychologically encourage the public's humanity and/or become a mediator for disaster relief. Disaster communication includes planning and the availability of information through the media (Lee, 2008). In addition to the coordination and media aspects, the cooperation aspect is also an important part of disaster management (LaFeber & Lind, 2008).

There are several other studies related to the role of communication in a disaster. There are conflicts at the grassroots level (victims) to the central government level. Sources of conflict varied, ranging from the distribution of aid during emergency response to reconstruction and

rehabilitation. The types of conflicts that occur vary, namely intrapersonal conflicts (stress), between groups (between volunteers, between donors, government versus NGOs, and government versus government), policy issues, and cases of corruption in earthquake relief funds (Lestari et al., 2010).

The factors that often become a problem are communication, information, coordination, and cooperation. Especially if it involves various institutions/components of society, the approach that needs to be known understood and implemented with humanitarian principles is a systems approach, which is a synergistic and integrated effort of the institution assigned to handle disasters and other supporting institutions, so that it becomes strong teamwork to carry out disaster risk reduction efforts.

There are several other studies related to the role of communication in a disaster. Such as technology and information sharing systems for natural disaster response (Bjerge, Clark, Fisker, & Raju, 2016; Usuda, Hanashima, Sato, & Sano, 2017; Waring et al., 2018), media content used to provide information to the public on disaster management (Amine & Meguenni, 2019; Chen, Gibbs, & Lin, 2021; Dong, Meng, Christenson, & Fulton, 2021), the use of networks in disaster detection (Alfalqi & Bellaiche, 2021; Ragini, Anand, & Bhaskar, 2018) and human behavior and perceptions in response to natural disasters (Endsley, Wu, Reep, Eep, & Reep, 2014; Tyshchuk & Wallace, 2018).

However, from previous studies, there are not many studies that emphasize several variables as system factors that have a contribution to disaster management. These variables include aspects of information sharing, collaboration, and coordination as independent variables, then the use of media as the dependent variable. Reduction as the dependent variable. So it is necessary to do further research on this matter. This study aims to analyze the significant contribution of the communication system in the form of information exchange (X1), collaboration (X2), and coordination (X3) to the use of media (Y1) in disaster management in Kendari City and North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

METHOD

The research was conducted in Kendari City and North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province with the consideration that these two areas in the last 10 (ten) years were one of the disaster-prone areas. Historically, Kendari City and North Konawe Regency have had a moderate to the high level of disaster risk. The high-risk level for earthquakes, landslides, floods, flash floods, droughts, extreme weather, extreme waves, and abrasion, as well as forest and land fires.

This research method uses a survey method with a quantitative research approach (Apuke, 2014; Gulraiz & Ali, 2021). In this study, the variables in question are information sharing (X1), cooperation (X2), coordination (X3) to the media (Y1). Sampling used proportional sampling technique, with a total sample of 60 samples consisting of Provincial BPBD, Kendari City BPBD, North Konawe Regency BPBD, Meteorology, Climatology and

Geophysics Agency (BMKG), National Search and Rescue Agency (Basarnas), National Army Indonesia (TNI), Indonesian National Police (POLRI), Indonesian Red Cross (PMI) Southeast Sulawesi, Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) Kendari City and North Konawe Regency, NGOs, Religious Leaders, Traditional Leaders, Community Leaders.

Data Collecting through questionnaires to respondents for primary data, as well as observation and interviews as complementary methods for data collection. Questionnaires are conducted by distributing a list of questions compiled based on data indicators that are operationalized from the variables to be studied to the officers selected as research samples (respondents), This method is used to explore primary data. The questionnaire was arranged in the form of a Guttman scale, a list of questions was compiled with five answer choices for each item. with the classification of very Incompatible, Incompatible, Neutral, Compatible, Very compatible.

The validity test used is product-moment correlation by correlating the answer scores on each question item with a total score, and for measuring reliability in this study using the Cronbach alpha method. The instrument is said to be reliable if the reliability coefficient is at least 0.60. Calculations for reliability testing were carried out with the help of the SPSS 25 computer program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), and coordination (X3) on the use of media (Y1) in disaster management in Kendari and North Konawe

Kendari City

The effect of the communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media (Y1) in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province can be determined using statistical analysis with the help of SPSS version 25.

The results of data analysis using SPSS version 25 show that the F_{count} value is 2.95 and the F_{table} value is 2.74, thus F_{count} 2.95 is greater than F_{table} 2.74. The conclusion that can be obtained from the results of the analysis is that there is an influence of the communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the communication system for natural disaster emergency response in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media for disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province, it can be seen in the value of R square in Table 1 below:

Table 1. The simultaneous effect between X1, X2, and X3 on Y1

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F. Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.504 ^a	.254	.168	9.82366	.254	2.952	3	26	.051

a. Predictors: (Constant), Coordination, Collaboration, Sharing Information

Source: SPSS version 25 data processing, 2020

for disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province by 0.504 or 50.4% and the remainder can be calculated using the following formula:

$$e = 1 - R^2$$

$$e = 1 - 0,504$$

$$e = 0.496$$

using exogenous independent variables in the form of information sharing, collaboration, and coordination communication systems by 50.4%. While the remaining 49.6% was caused by other variables outside this study.

To determine the contribution of each variable (information sharing, collaboration, and coordination) on the use of media in disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, it can be seen from the Beta value or standardized coefficient, while the t value is used for hypothesis testing. These figures can be seen in Table 2 of the coefficients below:

Table 2: The effect of variables X1, X2, and X3 on Y1

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	24.674	12.662		1.955	.061	-1.270	50.618
Sharing Information	.552	.220	.453	2.509	.019	.100	1.004
Collaboration	-.259	.154	-.300	-1.680	.105	-.576	.058
Coordination	.151	.155	.166	.972	.340	-.168	.469

a. Dependent Variable: Media

Source: SPSS version 25 data processing, 2020

the collaboration variable on the use of media in disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City is 30.0%, while the effect of the coordination variable on the use of media on disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City is 16.6%.

North Konawe

The effect of the communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media (Y1) in North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province can be determined using statistical analysis with the help of SPSS version 25.

The results of data analysis using SPSS version 25 show that the F_{count} value is 4.25 and the F_{table} value is 2.74, thus F_{count} 4.25 is greater than F_{table} 2.74. The conclusion that can be obtained from the results of the analysis is that there is an influence of the communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

This study aims to determine the magnitude of the influence of the communication system for natural disaster emergency response in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) on the use of media for disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. It can be seen in the value of R square in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Simultaneous effect of X1, X2, and X3 on Y1

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F. Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.574 ^a	.330	.252	10.32425	.330	4.259	3	26	.014

a. Predictors: (Constant), Coordination, Sharing Information, Collaboration

Source: SPSS version 25 data processing, 2020

disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province of 0.574 or 57.4 % and the remainder can be calculated using the following formula:

$$e = 1 - R^2$$

$$e = 1 - 0,574$$

$$e = 0.426$$

using exogenous independent variables in the form of a communication system in the form of information sharing, collaboration, coordination by 57.4%. While the remaining 42.6% is caused by other variables outside of this study.

To determine the contribution of each variable (information sharing, collaboration, and coordination) on the use of media for disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency, it can be seen from the Beta value or standardized coefficient, while the t value is used for hypothesis testing. These figures can be seen in Table 4 of the coefficients below:

Table 4. The effect of variables X1, X2, and X3 on Y1

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	9.493	10.353		.917	.368
Sharing Information	.453	.326	.272	1.388	.177
Collaboration	.171	.282	.181	.607	.549
Coordination	.221	.221	.265	1.003	.325

a. Dependent Variable: Media

Source: SPSS version 25 data processing, 2020

the effect of collaboration variables on the use of media on disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency is 18,1%, while the effect of the coordination variable on the use of media for disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency is 26.5%.

Information sharing variable (X1)

of the search for national disaster data from the Meteorology and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) that disaster data released in real-time is only limited to earthquake and weather data. Conceptually, the government's role in disaster management is very well planned, but in the implementation stage there are still many obstacles, especially in terms of disseminating disaster information, miscommunication and misinformation are still common.

addition, the results of the study also showed that the data and information sent seemed slow. The results of field observations also prove that disaster information in Kendari City and North Konawe Regency, such as floods, is not fast enough. Generally what happens is that new information reaches the public when the flood has occurred. Electronic media and even online media are busy reporting information on victims and damage caused by disasters.

Another interesting factor in sharing information is that the process of sending information from one person to another is very massive about disasters. It's just that this information is mostly about disaster events and some of it only provides information about bits and pieces of disaster events, as a result, it creates public confusion about the disaster information system. Instead of getting information that is integrated into a complete disaster information

system, the public gets incomplete information. This condition drags people into misunderstanding about disasters, even anticipating disasters.

The role of the media in providing disaster information should be positioned as an integral part of the disaster information system. The reality on the ground is that disaster information has very diverse sources. The National Disaster Management Agency operates its way in informing disasters, while in this system there are hundreds of sources of disaster information that appear, both from online media and social media. The phenomenon that occurs is that the government does not have the power to stem the flow of information from social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, and the like.

Social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, and the like tend to repeat or forward information to people or groups. On the other hand, there are not many efforts made by the government in sterilizing information which does not rule out the possibility that the information does not reflect the actual situation.

Collaboration Variable (X₂)

Collaboration has a long grace period. This is what distinguishes cooperation in a team. As a process, collaboration is an ongoing interaction between several people or groups. Collaborating requires joint planning so that the responsibility for implementation becomes a shared responsibility.

Collaboration is a mechanism that emphasizes joint planning in formulating policies, especially policies in disaster management. However, what happened in the field was the existence of a policy monopoly from the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) from the center to the regions. BNPB does not seem to involve other stakeholders in the formulation of disaster management policies.

From the results of the study, it was found that each institution which is an element that participates in disaster management has its structure. Under these conditions, there will be obstacles in communication lines, both between organizations involved in disaster management and between organizations and the community.

Communication channels both horizontally and vertically are very important in crisis communication (Fakhrudin 2007). Disaster management requires links or connections between organizations involved in disaster management. Although currently, the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) has a mechanism for sharing information and knowledge about disasters as regulated in the Regulation of the Head of the National Disaster Management Agency Number 21 of 2014 but it is only limited to BNPB's internal work units. In addition, through the Regulation of the Head of BNPB, it has also regulated the Disaster Communication Radio. However, this policy is not sufficient in the current disaster management. Disaster management requires mature and integrated collaboration.

Coordination Variable (X₃)

In disaster management activities, the involvement of several institutions other than the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) is very diverse, ranging from humanitarian agencies and non-humanitarian institutions such as the National Search and Rescue Agency (SAR), Fire Department, Indonesian Red Cross (PMI), Indonesian National Army (TNI)/ Police of the Republic of Indonesia (Polri), government agencies, educational institutions, political parties, NGOs and so on.

The role of the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) as the leading sector for disaster management has the authority to make policies. In the Regulation of the National Disaster Management Agency Number 5 of 2018 concerning Conditions and Procedures for the Implementation of Disaster Management in certain circumstances it is explained in Article 2 that one of the scopes regulated in the regulation is coordination meetings and procedures for implementing the implementation.

The results of the study indicate that the availability of standard operating procedures for disaster management has been stipulated in the Regulation of the Head of BNPB Number 02 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Preparing Standard Operating Procedures in the BNPB Environment. In every disaster management, coordination meetings and periodic meetings are held first.

Although coordination meetings have been held between agencies/institutions involved in disaster management, miscommunication often occurs in the field and even tensions occur between institutions. This condition indicates weak coordination in the implementation of disaster management.

Disaster communication management is a communication or coordination management activity that can reduce disaster risk or reduce the level of vulnerability and danger due to disasters. Disaster communication management is the responsibility of the central and regional governments together with the community in realizing maximum protection for the community and their assets from the possibility of a disaster. For decision-makers, both the central government, regional governments, natural disaster experts, and the community, it is hoped that communication will increase so that the implementation of disaster management as one of the priorities in national development can be realized properly in various regions in Indonesia.

Media Variable

Effective disaster communication requires the involvement of communication and information technology. The development of information technology is very rapid with the presence of an internet that can be accessed anywhere and anytime. This has led to a change in disaster communication from conventional communication media to modern and digital media via smartphones and cellular phones. The media has a very important role in the occurrence of disasters. The media is a channel that spreads information about disasters that

have spread to all corners of the world, including Indonesia. As well as information about the type of disaster, information about when a disaster occurs, information about the location of the disaster, the impact, and the needs of disaster victims can be memorized through the news.

Media is a forum for disseminating information, including information related to disasters. With the existence of disaster information, the public can understand the disaster as a whole, provided that the information about the disaster has accurate information value. In this case, communication competence is needed both in disseminating and accessing various disaster information. In this case, it takes people who understand how to collect valuable and accountable data, on the other hand, people need to understand how to access information.

For disaster events, what often happens is news from electronic media and online media only about news about the number of people who are victims of disasters. The function of the press in providing information about disaster events is very large, considering that the information conveyed through the media is very helpful for various parties, including the public, to obtain information about disasters that will and are happening. Various information conveyed through the media regarding disaster mitigation can reduce the risk of victims.

The results showed that the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) had collaborated with the media in providing disaster information in Kendari City and North Konawe Regency. These two areas provide information that cooperation with the media is very solid.

There are some print media in Southeast Sulawesi Province such as Kendari Pos and Rakyat Sultra. Apart from print media, there are several online media including Sultrakini.com, Penaaktual.com, Mysultra.com, Radarsultra.com, Tegas.com, Portalsultra.com, Mediakendari.com, Koransultra.com, Antarasultra.com. Liputan6.com, Kompas.com, and several other online media.

The media reports more about information during a disaster. The selection of disaster information by the media is inseparable from the news value of each media. This condition resulted in the information that should and needed by the public did not get attention from the media. Ideally, the media provide educational information or provide understanding to the public about the causes of disasters, but this kind of information is considered less desirable by the public. The tendency for people to be more interested in contradictory news, some think that bad news is good news. Only events or information from the negative side that people prefer.

Everyone, journalists and media consumers are more interested in an erupting volcano than a calm mountain (Vivian 2008). Media activists and media consumers are more interested in what has happened not what has not happened. It is undeniable that the audience is indeed more interested in news that has news value.

This condition requires the attention of the National Disaster Management Agency to be more proactive in efforts to build synergies with media crews to equalize perceptions about how to combine disaster information into news that has positive value in increasing public

understanding not only when the disaster occurs but also before the disaster. Positive news can also be interesting to read if it is packaged well so that many will like or share it on online media or even social media.

The interesting thing now is that everyone is a newsmaker with social media. People or groups can make news or share news according to their respective concepts. This condition allows the occurrence of news or information that cannot be accounted for. Even information from one social media such as WhatsApp can be shared to Facebook, Twitter, and other social media.

This condition is also a concern of the government in terms of disaster management agencies in identifying information sourced from social media. One of the steps that can be taken is to provide information education to the public about disaster problems, which is our shared responsibility. This educational model can be carried out in collaboration with media crews and academics and even communication practitioners in providing education to the community. The real example is providing training to the community, especially students and college students how to make short stories about disasters that are interesting. Provided an understanding of disaster information posted on social media by providing an understanding of how to create displayed content equipped with infographics or video graphics, images, text-based on valid data.

The media has a very important role in the occurrence of disasters. The media is a channel that spreads information about disasters that have spread to all corners of the world, including Indonesia. Media is the most significant mitigation tool for officials because its content creates awareness of disasters and risks. There are three actors in an effective disaster management process, namely government officials who present disaster information, the media that disseminate it, and the public who receive information and act (Perez-Lugo, 2001).

CONCLUSION

The communication system for responding to natural disasters in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) has a strong and significant simultaneous effect on the use of media (Y1) in reducing the risk of victims in North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The variable of media utilization can be explained by using exogenous independent variables in the form of a communication system in the form of information sharing, collaboration, and coordination. If tested separately (partial), then the variable of information sharing is the strongest but not significant on the use of media in disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in the North Konawe Regency.

In contrast to the conditions in Kendari City, the communication system for natural disaster emergency response in the form of information sharing (X1), collaboration (X2), coordination (X3) has a simultaneous but not significant effect on the use of media in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi Province. If tested

separately, the information sharing variable is influential and significant on the use of media in disaster management in reducing the risk of victims in Kendari City.

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